

Self-Regulated Learning Strategies and Oral Communication Skills among Maritime Students

Charles Ivan D. Posas^{1*}, Dennis B. Calitas¹, Roger B. Edil¹, Jermaine B. Repezo¹,
Vench F. Tanudtanud⁵ and Romel M. Pecajas^{1*}

¹DMMA College of Southern Philippines

*posascharlesivan@gmail.com

*romel.pecajas@deped.gov.ph

Date Submitted:
February 25, 2026

Date Accepted:
March 29, 2026

Date Published:
April 23, 2026

DOI:
10.5281/zenodo.19707090

ABSTRACT

This study dealt with the issue of effective oral communication skills among college students, particularly in maritime education where communication is essential to professional practice. The primary goal of this study was to determine how self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies influence the oral communication skills of Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines. This study utilized a quantitative non-experimental design employing correlational and predictive methods. It was conducted in a private higher education institution in Davao City with 335 first-year to third-year BSMT students as respondents, selected through random sampling to ensure equal

representation. A structured survey questionnaire was used to gather the data. Mean, Pearson r , and multiple regression analysis were the statistical tools used for data treatment employing correlational and predictive techniques. The results showed that self-regulated learning strategies ($M = 3.94$) and oral communication skills ($M = 3.88$) were on a high-level meaning that these are frequently expressed among students. A significant moderate positive relationship ($r = .555$, $p < .01$) was found between SRL strategies and oral communication skills. Furthermore, metacognitive strategy, learning strategy, motivational strategy, and contextual sensitivity significantly influenced oral communication skills, with contextual sensitivity identified as the strongest predictor, while environmental control and epistemological beliefs showed no significant influence. The study concludes that enhancing self-regulated learning strategies leads to improved oral communication skills among maritime students. It is therefore recommended that educators integrate SRL-based instructional strategies and provide more context-based communication activities to further strengthen students' communication competence in academic and professional settings.

Keywords: *self-regulated learning, oral communication skills, maritime students, and Davao City*

INTRODUCTION

Students are encouraged to have strong foundational oral communication skills, as these was needed to allow for student engagement and learning in the group environment. But at universities around the world, too many students are reported to be at a loss for words and too afraid to speak in public (OECD, 2021). Also, when students have difficulty with communication, they are less likely to get involved in class, they don't do as well in school, and they have a harder time finding a job after they graduate. The challenge of oral communication still prevails in universities across the world (Darling-Hammond et al., 2020). In

addition to this, poor oral communication is still a major obstacle to the employment and work readiness of graduates. Graduates are perceived globally to lack the oral communication skills necessary for teamwork, leadership and professional interaction (Jackson, 2022) which consequently puts them at a disadvantage in competitive work environments.

In China and Spain, students of all disciplines have difficulty speaking in public. The main reasons of this finding are related to communication apprehension, self-efficacy and the lack of chances to use the language (the oral communication in an effective way), Research in universities in China and Spain found that a large proportion of students are unwilling to participate in class discussions (Han, 2022; Osácar, 2021). Moreover, students who lack control over their own learning are more likely to struggle with interpersonal communication and adapting their speech to different situations, such as academic and social contexts. International studies indicate that limited learner autonomy is associated with poorer oral communication performance (Canbay, 2020). Therefore, students who lack autonomy or self-regulation in learning tend to experience greater difficulty in communicating effectively and adjusting their speech across various social and academic environments (Mushinin et al., 2025).

In the Philippines, people are worried about how students can communicate in English. This is a problem in colleges and universities. Many students lack confidence when speaking English because it is not their native language. Many students struggle with limited vocabulary, which makes it difficult for them to express ideas, especially when discussing academic topics. Several studies have also reported similar findings. (Mussa et al., 2020). In the Philippine national context, self-regulated learning has been examined among preservice teachers, revealing above average SRL skills, especially in environment structuring and goal-setting. However, students still face challenges with task strategies and assistance-seeking in virtual learning settings (Funa et al., 2023). Studies in the Philippines have also demonstrated that increased self-regulated learning is positively associated with students' proficiency in English, including speaking skills, suggesting that students who effectively manage their own learning tend to perform better in oral communication (Bravo, 2022).

In the local context, particularly within the Davao Region, the present study was conducted in a private university in Davao City, a setting that has been consistently identified in local literature as a site where oral communication difficulties among college students remain a pressing concern. Torrevillas (2022) examined first-year college students enrolled in the Purposive Communication course at a private university in Davao City and found that despite students' high self-perceived oral proficiency, qualitative data from focus group discussions exposed persistent speaking difficulties including shortfall of vocabularies, struggles with pronouncing words correctly, problems with sentence construction, and lack of mastery of subject-verb agreement. Such language deficiencies have direct negative effects on the students, who lack the skill to be accurate and confident in verbal communication assignments. Moreover, in their research at the University of the Immaculate Conception in Davao City, Raymunde and Mamonong (2022) found that college students did not display crucial indicators of language learning strategies use but low-level indicators of actual English proficiency, indicating that self-regulated language learning practices do not necessarily lead to improved oral communication performance, especially when foundational elements of vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. Finally, Ayawan et al. (2022) Supports this issue by reporting that the underlying oral communication barrier that college students encounter in a face-to-face communication environment is the lack of knowledge of the English language in particular in terms of vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation, enhanced by the psychological limitations that make students misinterpret meanings and experience mental blackouts when speaking. These convergent results of Davao City and surrounding regions highlight the need to explore the connection between self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills among college students in this region, because the ongoing shortcomings in speaking performance among students in this area demand a better comprehension regarding how independent and strategic learning behaviors could help students counter such problems.

Further evidence from the same region was provided by Orboc (2025), whose phenomenological study explored the teaching strategies used by eight Filipino language teachers of a certain school in augmenting the oral communication skills of the students. The study identified three key themes in their practice: Utilized Structured Performance and Assessment, Employed Interactive and Collaborative Oral Communication, and Maximized Digital Communication and Modern Platform. However, challenges such as students' non preference for Filipino, leading to low interest and confidence, and limited instructional variability, which hindered engagement, were also evident. Collectively, these local studies from the Davao Region affirm that oral communication skills remain both a pressing challenge and a central priority in Philippine classrooms, with interactive instruction, supportive learning environments, and responsive teacher strategies identified as key factors in strengthening learners' speaking abilities.

Although some scholars have studied students' autonomous learning and its effect on motivation and grades, research on its impact on students' communication skills is scant, especially at the tertiary level in the Philippines. Most research on testing and academic achievement doesn't consider how well students communicate with one another. In other words, we have very little sense of how students' own designs for learning, and the manner in which they manage their learning as they interact with others, connect with their abilities to talk and listen in the course of those activities. These levels influence each other; however, such elaboration is not reached in covert face-to-face interaction among the students. Self-regulated learning strategies, therefore, are of great importance in this context (Rum & Allo, 2023). Although prior research has high lightened test performance, they have not sufficiently examined their effects on oral communication skills. A little has been written on how self-regulation in learning, such as critical thinking about one's thinking process, control of the learning environment, and consciousness of one's surroundings, affects speaking ability. Although studies have indicated a beneficial association between self-regulated learning and oral communication skills, especially in English proficiency, its unique impact on oral communication performance still remains unexplored and is worthy of additional examination (Chansri et al., 2024). This highlights the need to investigate the potential role of SRL strategies in fostering improvements in students' communication skills. Analysis of this relationship can give further information of how the capacity to self-regulate learning is strongly related to effective communication (Ni'mah et al., 2025).

Studies indicate students who use SRL strategies have a higher chance of having better communication skills. By planning, monitoring and evaluating their own learning, they also become better equipped to handle their own anxiety, have a better understanding of how they need to tailor their message for a range of audiences and are better able to judge their effectiveness as communicators. Learners who are active in the learning task and who plan and reflect before and after undertaking a learning task with a higher degree of motivation, self-confidence, and oral proficiency (Schunk & Greene, 2020). Work Scope Practical communication effect Self-Regulation is also important in practical communication effect, such as when one calms oneself down or slows one speech - these are practical communication skills that are greatly required especially in areas of marine education where openness and precision are great values (Alam et al., 2021). Besides, the latest literature reviews indicate that students who practice self-regulation consistently not only achieve better learning outcomes but also improve their interpersonal communication, suggesting the potential of self-regulation to promote the development of both intellectual and social aspects (Kumar & Rajendran, 2022).

The results of this study were presented at the DMMA College of Southern Philippines, focusing on BSMT students. Results were disseminated through academic presentations, publications in peer-reviewed journals, and workshops with faculty and students. Furthermore, a hard copy of the study was uploaded to the school library for prospective home-grown researchers. Workshops help teachers integrate self-regulated learning strategies into language and communication instruction. Policy briefs were forwarded to the relevant academic authorities at college level, as far as the improvement of oral communication skills through the application of the strategies is possible. The concept is to promote a

deliberate implementation of research findings into practices in institutions. The research findings were also shared with Maritime Industry Authority (MARINA), so that the research findings can guide the national level maritime regulatory and training standards, making the study have a wider scope to influence policy and professional development initiatives in the industry in general.

Theoretical Framework

This study is primarily anchored on Zimmerman's Social Cognitive Theory of Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) and Communicative Competence Theory in second language acquisition. Zimmerman's SRL theory explains that learners are active participants in their own learning process through a cyclical model consisting of forethought (goal setting and planning), performance (self-monitoring and strategy use), and self-reflection (self-evaluation and adjustment). Contemporary research affirms that self-regulated learners effectively control their cognitive, motivational, and behavioral processes to achieve better academic outcomes (Panadero, 2020; Dignath & Veenman, 2021). In the context of this study, SRL theory explains the independent variable self-regulated learning strategies through its key components: metacognitive regulation, learning strategies, motivational strategies, contextual sensitivity, environmental control, and epistemological beliefs. These dimensions reflect students' abilities to schedule speaking tasks, monitor their language output, control their affective states, accommodate to audience members, and construct their learning environment. Schunk and Greene (2020) highlighted that those students who take part in this type of regulation are the ones more likely to obtain better academic and performance results, which involve communication practices.

The research is additionally situated within the concept of Communicative Competence, which presupposes that oral communication can be effective only if an individual has linguistic competence (predicate lexicon, grammatical knowledge, pronunciation) and sociolinguistic competence (expressed in the Canale & Swain model, revised in latest SLA researches). Accumulating evidence suggests that vocabulary depth and breadth are among the most powerful determinants of speech fluency and comprehensibility (Uchihara & Saito, 2021), whereas perception of grammatical well-formedness and pronunciation has a direct effect on intelligibility and listeners perceptions (Saito & Plonsky, 2020). Moreover, MacIntyre et al. (2020) has described that positive and negative emotional aspects of confidence vs. anxiety influenced oral performance and the association of SRL motivational regulation toward the outcomes of communication. Based on SRL and communicative competence paradigms, this study investigates the effects of: self-regulated learning strategies (independent variable) as the cognitive–motivational agency of restating facilitative in vocabulary, grammar and pronunciation in student's linguistic proficiency (dependent variable).

Conceptual Framework

The variables of the study are illustrated in Figure 1. The first construct is Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) Strategies, termed as Panadero (2020), who conceptualized self-regulated learning as an evolving and multidimensional process in which students strategically plan, monitor, regulate, and evaluate their cognitive, motivational, and behavioral learning activities. Zimmerman (2020) also stated that self-regulated learners are active agents who methodically formulate goals, use strategic learning methods, and participate in reflective evaluation to improve their learning. In the present research, SRL strategies are manifested in metacognitive items, learning strategy items, motivational strategies, contextual sensitivity, environmental control and epistemological beliefs. Metacognitive regulation helps learners plan strategically and monitor their speaking activities (Schunk & Greene, 2020); learning strategies are means which facilitate learners with specific procedures to better language learning (Teng & Zhang, 2022); motivational regulation is influential to learners' continuance in work despite of taking control of communication apprehension (Oga-Baldwin & Nakata, 2020); contextual competence enables learners to modify their speech in relation to different interlocutors and communicative circumstances (Teng, 2022);

environmental regulation helps learners avoid distractions and provides a good environment for speaking (Walach, 2020); and learners' epistemological beliefs have an influence on how learners view, construct, and evaluate knowledge (Greene et al., 2018). These models constitute the independent variable of the research.

Meanwhile, oral proficiency, as operationalized by the dependent variables, was students' competence in presenting ideas with clarity, accuracy, and effectiveness in spoken language. Zhang (2024) claimed that oral communication competence is determined by linguistic competence and psychological states. In this research, three key elements of oral communicative competence, namely vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation, are adopted to assess the participants' oral communicative skills. Several studies have substantiated that vocabulary knowledge is a significant contributor to speech fluency and comprehensibility (Uchihara & Saito, 2021). Grammatical proficiency helps provide coherent sentence-level ideas. It increases overall message comprehensibility (Saito & Plonsky, 2020), and pronunciation affects listener understanding and communication success (Shah et al., 2023). The theoretical model is based on the idea that SRL strategies directly affect oral communication capacity. In fact, students who engage in a continuous cycle of planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning are more likely to improve their vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation through well-organized practice and reflection. Hence, the investigation is based on the prediction that SRL strategies predict oral communication skills for BSMT students and that SRL is the vehicle by which speaking competence is enhanced.

Figure 1. *Conceptual Framework of the Study*

Statement of the Problem

This study aims to determine the relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills of BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines. Specifically, it seeks to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of self-regulated learning strategies of BSMT students in terms of:
 - 1.1 Metacognitive Strategy;
 - 1.2 Learning Strategy;
 - 1.3 Motivational Strategy;
 - 1.4 Contextual Sensitivity;
 - 1.5 Environmental Control; and

- 1.6 Epistemological Beliefs?
2. What is the level of students' oral communication skills in terms of:
 - 2.1 Vocabulary;
 - 2.2 Grammar; and
 - 2.3 Pronunciation?
3. Is there a significant relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and students' oral communication skills?
4. What domains of self-regulated learning strategies significantly influence students' oral communication skills?

Literature Review

This section presents the literature and studies related to the present study. The independent variable, self-regulated learning strategies, is factored into metacognitive strategies, learning strategy, motivational strategy, contextual sensitivity items, environmental control, and epistemological beliefs as discussed by Ni'mah et. al. (2020). On the other hand, the dependent variable, oral communication skills, is factored into vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation, as emphasized by Zhang (2024).

Self-Regulated Learning Strategies

In this study, Self-regulated learning strategies involve learners' capacity to plan, monitor, manage, and assess their own learning processes. These strategies involve how learners think about their learning, use appropriate learning techniques, manage their learning environment, and adjust their behavior according to different learning contexts. According to Panadero (2020), self-regulated learning is a multidimensional process that enables students to take active control of their cognitive, motivational, and behavioral learning processes. Similarly, Zimmerman (2020) explained that self-regulated learners are proactive individuals who set goals, employ strategies, and reflect on their learning outcomes to improve performance. Furthermore, Dignath and Veenman (2021) emphasized that self-regulated learning skills are essential in higher education because they enable students to adapt to complex academic tasks, including communication-intensive activities.

Metacognitive Strategy

Metacognitive items refer to students' ability to think about their own thinking, including planning, monitoring, and evaluating their learning and communication performance. These items help learners become aware of their strengths and weaknesses when engaging in learning and oral communication tasks. According to Schunk and Greene (2020), metacognition is essential for academic success as it enables learners to manage their comprehension and performance effectively. Hertel and Karlen (2020) found that implicit self-regulated learning (SRL) theories were more strongly associated with students' learning strategies, goal attainment, and metacognitive knowledge than implicit intelligence theories. In addition, these implicit SRL theories were barely related to students' personality and demographic variables. In addition, Zepeda et al. (2020) claimed that explicit metacognitive regulation positively impacts students' monitoring and adapting of their learning strategies leading to better academic performance and communication skills.

Learning Strategy

Self-regulated learning strategies in this study refer to the strategies or skills which learners use to plan, monitor, control, and reflect on their learning. In essence, these strategies influence students' perceptions about their learning, selection of appropriate methods, modification of the study environment, and response to situational changes in tasks or context. For instance, a learner may establish goals in advance, assess intermittently during an activity to determine what is effective, and subsequently modify procedures after identifying a deficiency. Xu and colleagues (2022) investigated these strategies in the

context of oral presentations with undergraduate EFL students. Their findings indicate that speaking challenges, planning, monitoring and rehearsal are commonly used by learners to cope with spoken difficulties and gradually lead to an enhancement of spoken performance. An individual may prepare a page containing key ideas, rehearse multiple times, and keep track of the time and lucidity while doing so. Similarly, Salde (2024) reported that maritime students were employ diverse language learning strategies to a moderate degree; however, it fluctuated among courses. This trend implies that they need specialized attention to enhance English proficiency and nurture more lucid, more sure oral contact. Specific advice as course-specific practice tasks or feedback on the structure of presentation may help a good deal. In addition, Foucart et al. (2021) noted that strategic language learning strategies correlate with speaking performance, especially when learners consciously choose strategies that align with task requirements.

Motivational Strategy

Refers to the internal drives and beliefs that sustain learners' engagement and persistence in academic tasks. Studies have shown that motivation plays a significant role in the effective use of SRL strategies, particularly in language learning contexts. In addition, Tang et. al. (2025) highlighted that students with higher levels of motivation, such as strong goal orientation and perceived autonomy, were more likely to employ intentional selfregulatory strategies, resulting in better learning outcomes. Based on Apat et al. (2023), the study found that students' level of oral communication was generally good and that better oral communication significantly influenced students' learning engagement, suggesting that when students communicate more effectively, they tend to be more engaged in their learning activities. Students' motivation and engagement toward oral communication influences their participation and involvement in learning. Nevertheless, OgaBaldwin and Nakata (2020) showed that motivated learners are more willing to participate in communicative activities, which increases engagement, persistence, and overall communication development.

Contextual Sensitivity

Contextual sensitivity items refer to students' awareness of the audience, situation, and social context in which learning and communication take place. This involves adjusting language use, tone, and communication strategies based on who they are speaking to and the setting. According to Teng (2022), contextual sensitivity is defined as learners' awareness of the audience and the specific situation in which communication takes place, which enables them to adjust their language, tone, and behavior appropriately for effective communication. Found that EFL learners who are aware of contextual clues, including audience and situation, perform better in oral communication tasks because this awareness helps them adjust their language and behavior appropriately for different social and professional settings. Zimmerman (2020) noted that self-regulated learners are more responsive to situational demands, allowing them to communicate appropriately across different contexts. Moreover, Nilsson (2020) stressed that self-regulated learners modify their communication strategies to the requirements of the task and the social context, which leads to better oral communication effectiveness. Therefore, contextual sensitivity plays a significant role in enabling students to communicate effectively and confidently across multiple academic and social environments.

Environmental Control

Environmental control items indicate the extent to which students intentionally manipulated their physical and social learning environment to promote good learning and communicative competence. This entails arranging the context of studying, minimizing distractions, and consulting with friends or teachers for help Mashwani and Damio (2022), Environmental control can be defined as students' capacity to influence or adjust their physical learning environment such as size of classroom, seating arrangement, access to learning resources, and general classroom environment to provide the supportive environment that foster students' English speaking and oral communication. In speaking, control over the environment

reduces speaking anxiety and increases students' comfort and confidence in speaking situations. Schunk and Greene (2020) underlined that Supportive learning environments act as powerful enhancers of students' engagement in oral contributions to discussions and presentations, thereby leading to better oral communication competence. Walach (2020) notes that environmental regulation is an essential facet of self-regulated learning, as it directs learners to become agents of their own performance, leading to communication tasks within academic and social environments.

Epistemological beliefs

In this study, epistemological beliefs are defined as students' implicit beliefs and assumptions about the nature of knowledge and the learning process, including what constitutes knowledge, the sources and certainty of knowledge, and the standards for evaluating knowledge. These beliefs influence how learners approach learning tasks, manage their own learning, and deal with challenging educational demands. Epistemological beliefs have been conceptualized as multidimensional and as significantly impacting learners' understanding, problem-solving capacity, and academic achievement (Schommer, 2022). From this perspective, Hofer and Pintrich (2021) argued that the epistemological beliefs of learners are one of the most critical factors in shaping their motivation and learning strategy as well as their self-regulation in learning. Students with strong beliefs about epistemology are more likely to perceive knowledge as tentative and warranted. However, individuals holding naïve beliefs tend to see knowledge as unified, certain, and handed down by authorities. This is the claim, if vaguely put, among Greene, Cartiff, and Duke (2020) identified that students with more sophisticated epistemological beliefs think more cognitively, critically appraise, and participate in self-regulated learning, all of which have positive implications for academic success. Likewise, such differences have shown a positive correlation with students' contribution in, and accomplishment of, tertiary education.

Oral Communication Skills

In the present study oral communication competence was defined as the students' ability to send clear and effective messages. such as motivation to speak, self-esteem while communicating, and an awareness of the audience and the context. Zhang (2024) emphasized that oral communication competence is a complex concept shaped by psychological and cognitive factors that shape learners' willingness, confidence, and ability to engage in spoken communication. MacIntyre et al. (2020) explained that Oral communication is significantly shaped by affective factors, including confidence, anxiety levels, and motivation, as well as situational awareness, which directly influence learners' engagement in spoken interaction.

Vocabulary

A word vocabulary is a prerequisite for oral and general language proficiency. Uchihara and Saito (2021) revealed that vocabulary size is a strong predictor of L2 speech fluency and comprehensibility, and highlighted that lexical knowledge directly affects online speech processing. Similarly, Dauletova and Rahimova (2020) explained that vocabulary acquisition is a pivotal point in language learning because it helps make sense and be functionally accurate. Moreover, contemporary evidence-based studies suggest that vocabulary accumulation is a strong predictor of academic achievement and of communicative confidence. Peters and Webb (2020) observed marked vocabulary-learning effects of intentional strategies, in particular spaced repetition and contextualized exposure, on retention and use. According to Nation (2022), the research also argues that the acquisition of high-frequency and academic vocabulary is a necessary condition for learners to participate effectively in academic and professional fields. Lexical proficiency was also found to be the strongest predictor of significant improvement in speech comprehensibility and a reduction in mental effort in a related longitudinal study of oral performance (Saito, 2021).

Grammar

Grammar is a fundamental part of spoken language, since it provides the organizational structure that enables a speaker to transmit ideas with clarity, coherence, and eloquence. Recent studies emphasize that grammatical competence supports intelligibility and comprehensibility in spoken interaction, particularly in academic and professional contexts where precision is necessary (Saito & Plonsky, 2020). Inaccurate grammatical structures can introduce ambiguity and undermine clarity, consequently influencing listeners' interpretation and comprehension of spoken messages. Studies also show that learners have difficulties with grammar in speaking due to crosslinguistic influence from their first language (L1) into the target language (L2), leading to fossilized errors and hesitation when speaking (Jarvis & Pavlenko, 2020). Furthermore, Aini (2024) found that students with better grammar knowledge were more likely to achieve higher scores in speaking tasks, which supports the idea that grammar contributes to the accuracy of spoken language and communicative clarity.

Pronunciation

Significantly influences the intelligibility of oral communication. These researchers reported that ESL teachers believe pronunciation should be integrated with other language skills, but their practices often do not align with those beliefs. Teachers sometimes neglect pronunciation, even when the curriculum emphasizes it, often due to time constraints or unclear instructional goals (Shah et al., 2023). Furthermore, ESL learners are aware of how their pronunciation classes are designed and are open to suggesting improvements. Learners value pronunciation instruction and think it should be meaningful and responsive to their needs, rather than ignored or superficially covered (Robin, 2022). Advanced technological feedback systems significantly improved ESL college students' pronunciation compared with traditional methods, suggesting the value of tech-assisted instruction (Ping, 2025).

METHODS

This chapter presents a comprehensive discussion of the methodologies employed in the study. It covers the overall research design that guides the investigation, the specific location where the study is conducted, and the characteristics of the participants involved. Furthermore, it describes in detail the research instruments used for data gathering, along with the procedures followed in collecting the necessary data. Lastly, this chapter explains the statistical tools and techniques applied in analyzing and interpreting the data to ensure accurate and reliable results.

Research Design

This study employs a non-experimental quantitative research design using correlational and predictive techniques to examine the relationship between Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies and Oral Communication Skills among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines. A correlational design is suitable for assessing the strength and direction of relationships between naturally occurring variables without requiring manipulation. (Creswell & Creswell, 2021). In this study, a correlation analysis evaluates the associations among SRL components, metacognitive regulation, learning strategies, motivational strategies, contextual sensitivity, environmental control, and epistemological beliefs, and oral communication indicators such as vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. Since they cannot be ethically or practically manipulated in the context of education, a non-experimental design is best suited for the study (Johnson & Christensen, 2020). Also, a multiple regression analysis was conducted to identify which SRL variables best predict OC and to assess the relative importance of each predictor (Tabachnick & Fidell, 2021).

Research Locale

This quantitative non-experimental study was conducted at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, located at Tigatto Road, Buhangin, Davao City, Region XI. This private higher education institution is known for its maritime and related fields, especially the Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT), which prepares students for careers in the global maritime industry. It fosters the development of oral communication skills (with an emphasis on English), an instrument for safe ship operation, and is instrumental for international cooperation in the shipping industry. The participants are BSMT students, and the study's setting enables a meaningful and appropriate investigation of the predictive power of Self-Regulated Learning (SRL) strategies for Oral Communication Skills.

Participants and Sampling Technique

The participants in this research were the 335; 113 for the first year, 111 for the second year, and 111 for 3rd year Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines for the School Year 2025-2026. The participants were 1st, 2nd, and 3rd-year students. These students were selected because they are currently engaged in maritime training, which requires them to employ self-regulated learning and oral communication skills for academic and professional survival. A random sampling method was used in order for every qualified BSMT student to have an equal opportunity of becoming a respondent, which minimizes bias, and a more representative sample would be attained. Accessibility and class schedules were taken into consideration in the selection to facilitate the smooth collection of data. The sample size of 335 respondents would be adequate to yield robust, valid findings in investigating the association between SRL strategies and Oral Communication Skills.

Research Instrument

This research is correlational in nature and a preplanned survey instrument utilized to gather information about the variables. The instrument was designed and adapted on the basis of authoritative SRL models and existing empirical investigation of SRL in oral communication (Panadero, 2020; Schunk & Greene, 2020). The relevant measures were selected and modified to suit the purposes of this study, primarily to measure SRL strategies and Oral Communication Skills among BSMT participants. The items measured students' planning, monitoring, strategy use, motivation, contextual awareness, environmental control, and learning beliefs. The response was scored on a five-point Likert scale, with 1 = "Strongly Disagree" and 5 = "Strongly Agree," and mean scores was computed to assess the respondent's level of SRL strategies.

Range of means	Categorical Response	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Always	Very High	The indicator is very highly observed.
3.40 - 4.19	Often	High	The indicator is highly observed.
2.60 - 3.39	Sometimes	Moderate	The indicator is moderately observed.
1.80 - 2.59	Rarely	Low	The indicator is slightly observed.
1.00 - 1.79	Never	Very Low	The indicator is not observed.

Table 1. *Self-Learning Regulated Strategies: Range of Means and Descriptions*

The second part of the questionnaire measured the dependent variable, Oral Communication Skills, as defined by Zhang (2024), as reported in "Oral Communication Competence and Its Influencing Factors in ESL Contexts." It was measured in the following areas: vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. A total of 10 items were used to assess the speaking competence, categorized under vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation. The responses were rated on an ordinal five-point Likert-type scale to assess the level of oral communication skills exhibited by the participants.

Range of means	Categorical Response	Description	Interpretation
4.20 - 5.00	Strongly Agree	Very High	The indicator is very highly manifested.
3.40 - 4.19	Agree	High	The indicator is highly manifested.
2.60 - 3.39	Neutral	Moderate	The indicator is moderately manifested.
1.80 - 2.59	Disagree	Low	The indicator is slightly manifested.
1.00 - 1.79	Strongly Disagree	Very Low	The indicator is not manifested.

Table 2. *Oral Communication Skills Range of Means and Descriptions*

Data Gathering

The information was collected by means of an orderly procedure. The researchers compose a written request for a stamped and endorsed letter from the research adviser's office to the dean of the maritime department. After the approval researcher shall make arrangements with the already selected BSMT classes' teachers to conduct the survey during the regular class meetings. The researchers coordinate with the Office of the College Registrar to secure the official list of 1st- to 3rd-year BSMT students for the Academic Year 2025–2026 to establish the sampling frame. A random sampling method was applied to provide equal chance for the respondents and to eliminate bias. The aim of the study is to be explained and voluntary informed consent was obtained from selected participants prior to dissemination of the questionnaires. Participants can be instructed clearly how to fill out the questionnaire to avoid any incorrect or untruthful answers. To standardize the delivery of the tool and improve return rates, the questionnaires were administered and collected by the researchers during class sessions. After collection, the data was checked, entered, and organized for statistical analysis. Finally, the collected data were tabulated and analyzed with the help of a statistician.

Data Analysis

The statistical data were analyzed with the help of the following tools: Mean. The mean was selected as the primary measure of central tendency to identify the average level of the variables examined. It was applied to answer the question 1 and 2. Pearson r. This tool was used to test whether there is an association between the two variables. It also used to answer the study's third research question. Regression Analysis. It is designed to model the dependence between two variables by fitting a linear equation to the observed data. This tool tests the fourth question of this study.

Ethical Consideration

The study strictly adhered to ethical standards to ensure the protection and welfare of all participants involved. Prior to the conduct of the study, a formal request letter was submitted to the authorities of DMMA College of Southern Philippines, and approval was secured from the appropriate offices before the data collection process commenced. The researchers coordinated with the Maritime Department and concerned faculty members to ensure that the study was conducted in an organized and authorized manner. The participants, who were Bachelor of Science in Marine Transportation (BSMT) students, were clearly informed about the purpose, procedures, and significance of the study. Participation in the research was entirely voluntary, and informed consent was obtained from all respondents prior to the administration of the survey questionnaire.

They were also assured that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any point without any form of penalty or consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained throughout the study. The researchers ensured that no personal identifiers were collected, and all responses were treated with utmost privacy and respect. The data gathered were used solely for academic purposes and were handled with integrity and responsibility. All collected information was properly stored, organized, and

secured to prevent unauthorized access or misuse. Furthermore, the researchers ensured the accuracy and reliability of the data by carefully recording, checking, and analyzing all responses. In presenting the findings, honesty and transparency were upheld to maintain the credibility and quality of the research. These ethical practices were observed to ensure that the study was conducted in a respectful, responsible, and professional manner.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This chapter analyzed the results of the study by gathering the respondents' responses about self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills among BSMT students at DMMA College of Southern Philippines, Inc. The results are grouped based on the sequence of the research questions, including the level of self-regulated learning strategies of BSMT students, the level of students' oral communication skills, the relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills, and the predictive influence of self-regulated learning strategies on students' oral communication skills.

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Metacognitive Strategy	0.70	3.92	High
Learning Strategy	0.72	3.97	High
Motivational Strategy	0.69	3.85	High
Contextual Sensitivity	0.66	4.08	High
Environmental Control	0.93	3.94	High
Epistemological Beliefs	0.92	3.91	High
Total	0.77	3.94	High

Table 1. *Level of Students' Self-Regulated Learning Strategies*

Level of Students' Social Media

Table 1 shows the level of self-regulated learning strategies. It has an overall mean of 3.94, which is described as high. This means that the self-regulated learning strategies are observed oftentimes. A standard deviation below 1.0 indicates that the responses are statistically the same. The findings are congruent with the study of Zimmerman and Schunk (2021), citing that high self-regulated learning (SRL) strategies refer to the degree to which learners actively take control of their own cognitive, motivational, and behavioral processes to achieve academic goals.

Individuals with high SRL are characterized by their ability to plan, monitor, and evaluate their learning progress without relying heavily on external guidance. Panadero and Alonso-Tapia (2022) cited that these learners set specific goals, select appropriate strategies, and adjust their approaches when they detect gaps between their intended and actual performance. Rather than being passive recipients of instruction, they engage deeply with content, reflect on their understanding, and exercise considerable agency over how and when learning occurs. The table shows the learners who established a high level of self-regulated strategies also exhibit effective metacognitive awareness, which allows them to reflect on their thinking, and make willful decisions related to study techniques, time management, and use of resources (Dignath and Veenman, 2021). This aspect of metacognition is highly related to intrinsic motivation because self-regulated learners are more likely to attribute success to effort and the use of strategies instead of innate ability. High SRL is also linked to resilience when faced with academic challenges; these students learn to see challenges as cues to improve their tactics instead of being viewed as demonstrating incompetence (Broadbent and Fuller-Tyszkiewicz, 2023).

Together, these attributes place high SRL as a core competency to lifetime academic and lifelong learning. Discoveries revealed that there is a high level of self-regulated learning strategies among BSMT

students. It indicates that self-regulated learning strategies are manifested often. Another revelation is that the self-regulated learning strategies are high in terms of metacognitive strategy. It further indicates that metacognitive regulation in learning is manifested usually. Students have a sense of how they think; they think first and then they participate in speaking activities, observe their performance during communication activities and reflect on how they can improve their performance after communication activities are finished. An example is that students reported that they are aware of their own weaknesses in vocabulary or grammar when they are about to speak in an activity and prepare accordingly.

Schunk and Greene (2020) agree with this discovery because they highlighted that metacognition is a crucial factor in academic performance since it allows learners to control their understanding and achievements. Likewise, Zepeda et al. (2020) affirmed that explicit metacognitive regulation positively impacts students' monitoring and adapting of their learning strategies, leading to better academic performance and communication skills. Additionally, Hertel and Karlen (2020) discovered that self-regulated learning theories are closely linked to the strategies of learning, accomplishing the learning goals, and having metacognitive knowledge among students, which implies that those students who contemplate learning are more likely to succeed.

Furthermore, discoveries revealed that there is a high level of self-regulated learning strategies in terms of learning strategy. It further indicates that the use of learning strategies in managing academic tasks is manifested usually. Results illustrate that students employ a variety of strategies to improve their language learning, such as planning key ideas before oral presentations, rehearsing their speech multiple times, and monitoring their time and clarity during delivery. Students also disclosed that they seek out English-language media and practice speaking independently to supplement classroom instruction. This outcome is consistent with Xu et al. (2022), who investigated learning strategies in oral presentations among undergraduate EFL students and found that planning, monitoring, and rehearsal are commonly used by learners to cope with spoken difficulties and gradually lead to an enhancement of spoken performance.

Additionally, Foucart et al. (2021) noted that strategic language-learning strategies correlate with speaking performance, especially when learners consciously choose strategies that align with task requirements. Similarly, Salde (2024) reported that maritime students employ diverse language learning strategies; however, effectiveness fluctuates across courses, suggesting that more focused and course-specific practice tasks and feedback on presentation structure may help greatly. What is more, discoveries revealed that there is a high level of self-regulated learning strategies in terms of motivational strategy. It further indicates that motivational regulation in learning is manifested usually. Results further unveil that students are driven by a desire to communicate effectively in professional maritime settings, which motivates them to persist in learning and engaging in communicative tasks. Students also reported that they set personal communication goals and push themselves to participate in class discussions despite experiencing anxiety or discomfort.

This finding is in consonance with Oga-Baldwin and Nakata (2020), who showed that motivated learners are more willing to participate in communicative activities, which increases engagement, persistence, and overall communication development. Likewise, Tang et al. (2025) also emphasized that students who had greater motivation, high goal orientation, and perceived autonomy had a greater tendency to use intentional self-regulatory strategies, leading to improved learning outcomes. Apat et al. (2023) have also confirmed these results as they have discovered that motivation and engagement of students towards oral communication have a significant impact on their participation and involvement in learning activities.

Among the six indicators in total, contextual sensitivity has got the highest rating and its mean rating is 4.08 or high which means that awareness as regards to audience and situational context of communication is exhibited by students frequently. Findings depict how students readily adapt their tone, use of language, and style of communication based on the context of communicating. Additionally, Foucart et al. (2021) noted that strategic language-learning strategies correlate with speaking performance, especially when learners consciously choose strategies that align with task requirements. Similarly, Salde

(2024) reported that maritime students employ diverse language learning strategies; however, effectiveness fluctuates across courses, suggesting that more focused and course-specific practice tasks and feedback on presentation structure may help greatly.

What is more, discoveries revealed that there is a high level of self-regulated learning strategies in terms of motivational strategy. It further indicates that motivational regulation in learning is manifested usually. Results further unveil that students are driven by a desire to communicate effectively in professional maritime settings, which motivates them to persist in learning and engaging in communicative tasks. Students also reported that they set personal communication goals and push themselves to participate in class discussions despite experiencing anxiety or discomfort. This finding is in consonance with Oga-Baldwin and Nakata (2020), who showed that motivated learners are more willing to participate in communicative activities, which increases engagement, persistence, and overall communication development.

Likewise, Tang et al. (2025) also emphasized that students who had greater motivation, high goal orientation, and perceived autonomy had a greater tendency to use intentional self-regulatory strategies, leading to improved learning outcomes. Apat et al. (2023) have also confirmed these results as they have discovered that motivation and engagement of students towards oral communication have a significant impact on their participation and involvement in learning activities. Among the six indicators in total, contextual sensitivity has got the highest rating and its mean rating is 4.08 or high which means that awareness as regards to audience and situational context of communication is exhibited by students frequently. Findings depict how students readily adapt their tone, use of language, and style of communication based on the context of communicating with peers, instructors, or when presenting in a formal context. Students have revealed that they tend to know when to use a formal or informal language and make a conscious effort to adjust their messages to the situation they are in at the time of communication.

This result is justified by Teng (2022), who concluded that EFL learners possessing information about the context, such as audience and situation, can accomplish oral communication tasks more successfully since such information allows them to modify the language and behavior to fit in different social and professional contexts. Zimmerman (2020) also expressed that self-regulated learners are more attentive to the situational demands, which enable them to express themselves in a proper way in various circumstances. This is also reminiscent of Nilsson (2020), who emphasized that self-regulated learners adjust to the needs of the task and the social situation by changing their communication strategies, resulting in their increased oral communication effectiveness.

Furthermore, it was found that self-regulated learning strategies are highly in terms of environmental control. It further indicates that students' management of their learning environment is manifested usually. Students said that they intentionally selecting quiet and distraction-free environments during English study or when preparing to speak are effective, and that they seek peer or teacher assistance when they have learning problems. They are also aware of how they arrange their study area to enable them to learn effectively and to practice orally. This finding compares with Mashwani and Damio (2022) who described environmental control as the ability of students to manipulate or modify their physical learning surroundings such as classroom size, seating pattern, and access to learning resources to make English speaking and oral communication effective. In addition, Schunk and Greene (2020) underlined that supportive learning environments act as powerful enhancers of students' engagement in oral contributions to discussions and presentations, leading to better oral communication competence. Walach (2020) also points out that environmental regulation is a critical aspect of self-regulated learning because it guides learners to be agents of their performance in communication activities in academic and social settings.

Finally, discoveries revealed that there is a high level of self-regulated learning strategies in terms of epistemological beliefs. It further indicates that students' beliefs about the nature of knowledge and learning are manifested usually. Students expressed beliefs that English communication is a skill that can

be improved through dedicated effort and practice, and that their current limitations in speaking are not permanent but can be overcome through systematic learning. They view knowledge as something constructed gradually through experience rather than fixed and absolute. These findings are aligned with the notions of Hofer and Pintrich (2021), who argued that the epistemological beliefs of learners are critical factors in shaping their motivation, learning strategy use, and self-regulation. Likewise, Greene et al. (2020) identified that students with more sophisticated epistemological beliefs think more critically, appraise information more carefully, and participate in self-regulated learning, all of which have positive implications for academic success. Moreover, Schommer (2022) conceptualized epistemological beliefs as multidimensional and as significantly impacting learners' understanding, problem-solving capacity, and academic achievement.

Level of Oral Communication Skills

Presented in Table 2 is the level of students' oral communication skills. The overall mean score obtained of students' oral communication skills is 3.88 or high and the standard deviation is 0.58. This means that students' oral communication skills are often observed. Specifically, the mean ratings of the indicators of students' oral communication skills are disclosed as follows: grammar obtained the highest category mean rating of 3.92 or high with a standard deviation of 0.67; pronunciation attained a category mean rating of 3.87 or high with a standard deviation of 0.68; and vocabulary obtained a category mean rating of 3.85 or high with a standard deviation of 0.63.

Discoveries revealed that there is a high level of students' oral communication skills. It indicates that students' oral communication skills are manifested often. It is also unveiled that there is a high level of students' oral communication skills in terms of vocabulary. It further indicates that vocabulary use in oral communication is manifested usually. Students recognize the importance of selecting appropriate words when speaking; they understand that using the right vocabulary helps convey their ideas more clearly and confidently in both academic and social settings. However, it can be noted that while students frequently use familiar vocabulary, they still experience difficulty when expressing themselves in technical or academic contexts where word choice is more demanding.

Table 2. *Level of Students Oral Communication Skills*

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Vocabulary	0.63	3.85	High
Grammar	0.67	3.92	High
Pronunciation	0.68	3.87	High
Total	0.58	3.88	High

This finding is consistent with Uchihara and Saito (2021), who revealed that vocabulary size is a strong predictor of second language speech fluency and comprehensibility, and that lexical knowledge directly affects online speech processing. Furthermore, Dauletova and Rahimova (2020) reinforced this finding by explaining that vocabulary acquisition is pivotal to language learning because it enables learners to make sense of ideas and be functionally accurate in spoken communication. These discoveries align with the work of Nation (2022), who argued that the acquisition of high-frequency and academic vocabulary is a necessary condition for learners to effectively participate in academic and professional contexts.

Furthermore, discoveries revealed that there is a high level of students' oral communication skills in terms of grammar. It further indicates that grammatical use in oral communication is manifested usually. Results illustrate that students generally construct sentences when speaking, though they sometimes commit grammatical errors that affect the clarity of their message. Students acknowledged that proper grammar contributes to how well they are understood, particularly in formal and professional communication settings. The only item which attained the highest mean rating among the three indicators is grammar, which

suggests that students tend to be more aware of grammatical structures than other components of oral communication.

This result supports the findings of Saito and Plonsky (2020), who emphasized that grammatical competence supports intelligibility and comprehensibility in spoken interaction, particularly in academic and professional contexts where precision is required. Similarly, Aini (2024) found that students with better grammar knowledge were more likely to achieve higher scores in speaking tasks, reinforcing the idea that grammar contributes to the accuracy and communicative clarity of spoken language. Moreover, Jarvis and Pavlenko (2020) noted that learners have difficulties with grammar in speaking due to cross-linguistic influence from their first language into the target language, leading to fossilized errors and hesitation when speaking.

Furthermore, findings exposed that there is a high level of students' oral communication skills in terms of pronunciation. It further indicates that pronunciation in oral communication is manifested usually. Results further unveil that students are generally aware of how their pronunciation affects listener comprehension; they make conscious efforts to pronounce words correctly, particularly when speaking in front of peers or instructors. Students also noted that mispronunciation often causes them embarrassment and reduces their confidence during oral tasks. This finding is in consonance with Shah et al. (2023), who reported that ESL teachers believe pronunciation should be integrated with other language skills, as it significantly influences the intelligibility of oral communication.

Likewise, Robin (2022) found that learners value pronunciation instruction and believe it should be meaningful and responsive to their needs, rather than superficially covered. Additionally, Ping (2025) found that advanced technological feedback systems significantly improved ESL college students' pronunciation compared to traditional methods, suggesting the value of technology-assisted instruction in developing this critical oral communication component.

Correlation Between Measures

Table 3. *Relationship Between Self-Regulated Learning Strategies and Oral Communication Skills*

	r	p	Decision	Interpretation
Self-Regulated Learning Strategies and Oral Communication Skills	.555**	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant

Note: **Significant at $p < .01$

Shown in Table 3 is the relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills of BSMT students. The result shows a p-value of .000, which is less than the .01 level of significance, thereby rejecting the null hypothesis. This means there is a significant relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills. The r-value of .555 represents the moderate positive relationship between the two variables. This means that those students who use more effective self-regulated learning strategies are more likely to have better oral communication skills.

The positive and moderate relationship among self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills is significant and is similar to that of Ni'mah et al. (2025) whose research found that there was a positive relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and oral communication skills of students, indicating that higher self-regulated students are more likely to have better speaking skills. Their research also suggested that in order to increase their speaking, students used three stages of SRL such as forethought, performance or volitional control, and selfreflection and the close connection between strategic self-regulation and spoken language proficiency was emphasized. Likewise, Chansri et al. (2024) confirmed that despite the studies that have suggested that self-regulated learning has a positive relationship with oral communication skills, particularly in English proficiency, its distinct effect on oral communication performance has yet to be explored, and the present study is a valuable addition to this scientific base.

The result also corroborates the work of Schunk and Greene (2020), who highlighted that learners who actively participate in self-regulatory cycles of planning, monitoring, and evaluating are more likely to obtain better academic and performance results, which include communication practices. Collectively these results confirm that the extent to which students can actively regulate their own learning is significantly related to how well they can communicate orally, which supports the importance of promoting self-regulated learning behaviors as a means to improve the oral communication skills of college students.

Regression Analysis of Self-Regulated Learning Strategies and Oral Communication Skills

Table 4. *Domains of Self-Regulated Learning Strategies Influencing Oral Communication Skills*

Indicators	B	p	Decision	Interpretation
(Constant)	1.380	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Metacognitive Strategy	.133	.006	Reject H ₀	Significant
Learning Strategy	.102	.031	Reject H ₀	Significant
Motivational Strategy	.099	.039	Reject H ₀	Significant
Contextual Sensitivity	.247	.000	Reject H ₀	Significant
Environmental Control	.075	.086	Accept H ₀	Not significant
Epistemological Beliefs	-.028	.399	Accept H ₀	Not significant

Table 4 presents the domains of self-regulated learning strategies that affect oral communication skills. The results indicate that environmental control ($p = .086$) and epistemological beliefs ($p = .399$) have p-values exceeding the .05 level of significance. Therefore, these two factors are not considered to have a significant influence on oral communication skills.

Among the four significant domains, contextual sensitivity emerged as the strongest predictor of oral communication skills with the highest beta coefficient ($B = .247$, $p = .000$). This finding is well-supported in the existing literature. Research on situational language learning confirms that students who are aware of the differences between formal and informal communication styles, understand the suitable language for each conversational situation, and are sensitive to the audience and context of their speaking tasks consistently demonstrate stronger oral communication performance.

This is directly aligned with Teng (2022), who defined contextual sensitivity as learners' awareness of the audience and the specific situation in which communication takes place, enabling them to adjust their language, tone, and behavior appropriately for effective communication. In the maritime education context, where BSMT students are expected to interact with officers, crew members, port authorities, and international counterparts in varied communicative settings, the ability to regulate one's speech according to context becomes a highly critical skill.

Students who are attuned to their communicative environment understanding when to use technical maritime language versus everyday communication are better positioned to express themselves clearly, accurately, and appropriately. Zimmerman (2020) further reinforced this by noting that self-regulated learners are more responsive to situational demands, allowing them to communicate appropriately across different contexts, which directly translates into more effective oral communication performance.

Furthermore, the strong predictive influence of contextual sensitivity on oral communication skills is consistent with the broader argument in self-regulated learning literature that situational awareness is not merely a social skill but a cognitive-regulatory strategy. Given that contextual constraints tend to directly impact efforts at self-regulation, examining how self-regulated learning strategies interact with situational variables in ESL/EFL contexts is of great importance, particularly in settings where the medium of instruction differs from students' first language. Nilsson (2020) similarly affirmed that self-regulated learners who modify their communication strategies to suit task requirements and social context achieve better oral communication effectiveness.

This implies that BSMT students who are more contextually sensitive adjusting vocabulary, tone, and delivery based on the communicative situation are more likely to perform better in vocabulary, grammar, and pronunciation tasks that require situationally appropriate language use. These findings collectively suggest that developing students' contextual sensitivity through targeted communicative tasks, role-playing in professional maritime scenarios, and reflective speaking activities can meaningfully strengthen their overall oral communication skills.

CONCLUSION

Finally, the research gives solid evidence that maritime students have a high degree of self-regulated learning strategies especially in contextual sensitivity, learning strategies, and metacognitive strategies, all of which make them assume an active control of their learning processes. Meanwhile, oral communication skills of students are very high, and grammar, pronunciation and vocabulary are the most developed aspects that can facilitate effective communication.

The results also validate that self-regulated learning strategies are important in improving oral communication skills. The strong correlation between the two variables shows that the more the students are strategic, reflective, and motivated in their learning, the better their oral communication skills are.

More to the point, the findings of the regression indicate that metacognitive strategy, learning strategy, motivational strategy, and contextual sensitivity are the key predictors of oral communication skills, with contextual sensitivity being the most significant predictor. This highlights the significance of the aptitude of the students to adjust their communication in accordance with the audience, purpose and circumstance, particularly in maritime conditions where proper communication is paramount. These findings, in general, indicate that the process of creating self-regulated learners is a key to creating effective communicators.

By training students to plan, monitor, evaluate and adjust their learning behaviors, they are not only able to become better students, but also more confident and proficient in the representation of ideas. This has great implications on maritime education where communication is vital to safety, coordination and professional performance. Therefore, the implementation of self-regulated learning strategies in the teaching process, as a means of oral communication competence, could be reinforced even further by designing speaking tasks, reflective assignments, and communication tasks based on the context. However, the research underlines that cultivating self-regulated learning is not only an educational practice but an essential route towards the creation of adaptive, independent and globally professional maritime workers that are able to communicate effectively in multicultural and dynamic settings.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusions, it is recommended that:

1. The maritime students may continuously practice self-regulated learning strategies such as planning, monitoring, and adapting their communication to improve their oral skills.
2. The school's English instructor may integrate metacognitive, motivational, and context-based speaking activities to enhance students' oral communication competence.
3. The students' parents may support and encourage consistent English communication practice at home to reinforce students' confidence and language development.
4. MARINA may promote communication-focused training programs that strengthen maritime students' practical and professional speaking skills.
5. The future researchers may explore additional variables or conduct longitudinal studies to further examine the development of self-regulated learning and communication skills.

6. School administrators may implement institutional programs and policies that foster self-regulated learning and provide more opportunities for structured oral communication practice.

References

- Aini D. V. (2024). A Study on the Relationship Between Grammar Proficiency and Oral Communication Performance of Intensive English Course Participants <https://ejournal.unhasy.ac.id/index.php/TEFLIC/article/view/10740?>
- Alam, S. P., Mahmood, T. R., & Singh, N. S. (2021). Exploring the role of self-regulated learning in the development of oral communication skills among university students. *Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 11(4), 112–125. <https://www.journals.elsevier.com/journal-of-applied-linguistics>
- Alrabai, F. (2020). Exploring the effects of anxiety, motivation, and self-efficacy on learners' oral performance. *System*, 95, 102360. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2020.102360>
- Apat, H. C. M., Sarias, K. J. M., Tomarong, M. T., & Bacatan, J. R. (2023). The influence of oral communication on the learning engagement of students. *Canadian Journal of Language and Literature Studies*, 3(4), 44–58. <https://doi.org/10.53103/cjlls.v3i4.104>
- Ayawan, J. E., Duyapat, N. O., & Martin, A. B. (2022). An analysis of the oral communication barriers in face-to-face communications towards the development of an intervention program in speaking. *Technium Social Sciences Journal*, 31(1), 183–202. <https://doi.org/10.47577/tssj.v31i1.6487>
- Bai, S., Hew, K. F., & Huang, B. (2020). Does gamification improve student learning outcome? Evidence from a meta-analysis and synthesis of qualitative data in educational contexts. *Computers & Education*, 157, 103948. <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1747938X19302908>
- Bravo, V. B. (2022). Self-regulated learning skills and English proficiency. *Journal of Education, Society and Behavioural Science*, 35(7), 40–51. <https://journaljesbs.com/index.php/JESBS/article/view/1153>
- Broadbent, J., & Fuller-Tyszkiewicz, M. (2023). Self-regulated learning and academic achievement in online education: A systematic review. *Educational Psychology Review*, 35(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-022-09743-3>
- Canale, M. A., & Swain M., (2022). Theoretical Bases of Communicative Approaches to Second Language Teaching and Testing. https://www.researchgate.net/publication/31260438_Theoretical_Bases_of_Communicative_Approaches_to_Second_Language_Teaching_and_Testing
- Canbay, F. (2020). The relationship between self-regulation and use of language learning strategies in secondary school students. ERIC. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1259097.pdf>
- Chansri, C., Kedcham, A., & Polrak, M. (2024). The relationship between self-regulated learning strategies and English language abilities and knowledge of undergraduate students. *LEARN Journal: Language Education and Acquisition Research Network*, 17(1), 286–307. <https://files.eric.ed.gov/fulltext/EJ1415587.pdf>
- Chansri, C., Wasanasomsithi, P., & Prapphal, K. (2024). Self-regulated learning and oral communication performance among EFL learners: A review and future directions. *PASAA: Journal of Language Teaching and Learning in Thailand*, 67(1), 45–72.
- Darling-Hammond, L., Flook, L., Cook-Harvey, C., Barron, B., & Osher, D. (2020). Implications for educational practice of the science of learning and development. *Applied Developmental Science*, 24(2), 97–140. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10888691.2018.153779>
- Dauletova D. & Rahimova D. (2020) The Importance of Vocabulary in Language Learning https://www.researchgate.net/publication/367220693_THE_IMPORTANCE_OF_VOCABULARY_IN_LANGUAGE_LEARNING
- Dauletova, V., & Rahimova, A. (2020). Vocabulary acquisition as a pivotal point in language learning and functional accuracy. *Journal of Language Teaching and Research*, 11(3), 401–408. <https://doi.org/10.17507/jltr.1103.05>
- Dignath, C., & Veenman, M. V. J. (2021). The role of direct strategy instruction and indirect activation of self-regulated learning Evidence from classroom observation studies. *Educational Psychology Review*, 33(2), 489–533. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-020-09556-0>

- Foucart, A., et al. (2021). Foreignness or processing fluency? On understanding the negative bias toward foreign accented speakers. *Language Learning*. <https://onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1111/lang.12413>
- Foucart, A., Ruiz-Tada, E., & Costa, A. (2021). Strategic language-learning strategies and speaking performance in EFL contexts. *Language Learning Journal*, 49(3), 311–325. <https://doi.org/10.1080/09571736.2019.1567678>
- Funa, A. A., Gabay, R. A. E., Deblois, E. C. B., Leros, L. D., & Jetomo, F. G. J. (2023). Exploring Filipino preservice teachers' online self-regulated learning skills and strategies amid the COVID-19 pandemic. *Social Sciences & Humanities Open*, 7(1), 100470. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssaho.2023.100470>
- Greene, J. A., Cartiff, B. M., & Duke, R. F. (2020). A meta-analytic review of the relationship between epistemological beliefs and self-regulated learning. *Educational Psychology Review*, 30(1), 267–296. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10648-017-9393-3>
- Han, S. (2022). Impact of foreign language classroom anxiety on higher education students. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 945062. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2022.945062>
- Hertel, S., & Karlen, Y. (2020). Implicit theories of self-regulated learning and their relation to SRL outcomes. *Metacognition and Learning*, 15(1), 21–46. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11409-019-09211-2>
- Hofer, B. K., & Pintrich, P. R. (2021). The development of epistemological theories: Beliefs about knowledge and knowing and their relation to learning. *Review of Educational Research*, 67(1), 88–140. <https://doi.org/10.3102/00346543067001088>
- Jackson, J. (2022). Reticence and anxiety in oral English classrooms: A mixed-methods study. *System*, 106, 102750. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2022.102750>
- Jarvis, S., & Pavlenko, A. (2020). *Crosslinguistic influence in language and cognition*. Routledge. <https://www.taylorfrancis.com/books/mono/10.4324/9780203935927/crosslinguistic-influence-language-cognition-scott-jarvis-aneta-pavlenko>
- MacIntyre, P. D., et al., (2020). Expanding the theoretical base for the dynamics of willingness to communicate. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 10(1), 111–132. <https://pressto.amu.edu.pl/index.php/ssllt/article/view/22352>
- Mashwani, H. U., & Damio, S. M. (2022). Environmental control and oral communication competence in ESL classrooms. *Journal of Language and Linguistic Studies*, 18(1), 102–118.
- Mussa, A., et al. (2020). Examining the issues of gender and indigenous knowledge in English education semester courses. *Journal of English Education*, 5(2), 104–116. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/348015335>
- Nilsson, M. (2020). Language learning strategies and beyond: A look at strategies in the context of self-regulation. *Studies in Second Language Learning and Teaching*, 10(2), 239–263. <https://pressto.amu.edu.pl/index.php/ssllt/article/view/23353>
- Nilsson, P. (2020). Self-regulation and oral communication performance in higher education. *Scandinavian Journal of Educational Research*, 64(4), 578–591. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00313831.2019.1595718>
- Ni'mah, U., Nasihah, M., & Munfaati, F. (2025). Exploring self-regulated learning strategies to enhance English speaking skills among EFL students. *Indonesian Journal of Applied Linguistics*, 14(3), 472–483. <https://ejournal.upi.edu/index.php/IJAL/article/view/72000>
- OECD. (2021). *Education at a glance 2021: OECD indicators*. OECD Publishing. <https://doi.org/10.1787/b35a14e5-en>
- Oga-Baldwin, W. L. Q., & Nakata, Y. (2020). Engagement, gender, and motivation: A predictive model for Japanese young language learners. *System*, 89, 102168. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/312799633>
- Orboc, M. L. (2025). Rekindling skills in oral communication: Strategies of Filipino language teachers. *EPRA International Journal of Environmental Economics, Commerce and Educational Management*, 12(7). <https://doi.org/10.36713/epra0414>
- Panadero, E. (2020). A review of self-regulated learning: Six models and four directions for research. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 11, 570. <https://doi.org/10.3389/fpsyg.2017.00422>
- Panadero, E., & Alonso-Tapia, J. (2022). Self-assessment: Theoretical and practical connotations. *Psicología Educativa*, 28(1), 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.5093/psed2021a24>
- Ping L, (2025) Innovative approaches to English pronunciation instruction in ESL contexts: integration of multi-sensor detection and advanced algorithmic feedback <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/articles/PMC11795553/>
- Peters, E., & Webb, S. (2020). Incidental vocabulary acquisition through viewing L2 television and factors that affect learning. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 42(3), 551–577. DOI: 10.1017/S0272263117000407

- Raymunde, P. P., Jr., & Mamonong, V. H. (2022). Unfolding the lived experiences of the college students' language learning strategies vis-à-vis their English proficiency: A convergent design. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 4(3), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.36892/ijlls.v4i2.805>
- Robin, C. J. (2022). To Say or Not to Say: ESL Learners' Perspective towards Pronunciation Instruction <https://jurnal.unsil.ac.id/index.php/jelita/article/view/4308?>
- Rum, E. P., & Allo, M. D. (2023). The analysis of self-regulated learning in improving speaking skills at the classroom context. *ResearchGate*. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/369900720>
- Salde, H. J. G. (2024). Language learning strategies of maritime students. *GEO Academic Journal*, 5(1). <https://geoacademicjournals.com/current/volume-5-no-1/language-learning-strategies-of-maritime-students/>
- Saito, K., & Plonsky, L. (2020). Effects of second language instruction on speech comprehensibility and accuracy. *Studies in Second Language Acquisition*, 41(2), 239–263. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/331271213>
- Saito, K., & Plonsky, L. (2020). Effects of second language pronunciation teaching revisited: A proposed measurement framework and meta-analysis. *Language Learning*, 70(3), 654–708. <https://doi.org/10.1111/lang.12392>
- Schommer, M. (2022). Effects of beliefs about the nature of knowledge on comprehension. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 82(3), 498–504. <https://doi.org/10.1037/0022-0663.82.3.498>
- Schunk, D. H., & Greene, J. A. (2020). *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (2nd ed.). Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315697048>
- Shah et. al., (2023). The Pronunciation Component in Esl Lessons: Teachers' Beliefs and Practices <https://ejournal.upi.edu/index.php/IJAL/article/view/4844?>
- Shah, M., Mahmood, M., & Ali, A. (2023). ESL teachers' beliefs and practices in pronunciation instruction. *English Language Teaching*, 16(4), 55–67. <https://doi.org/10.5539/elt.v16n4p55>
- Tang, S., Wang, Z., Jiang, M., Jimenez, D. D., & Zhang, L. (2025). Motivation and self-regulated learning among online English learners: Profiles and pedagogical implications. *Education Sciences*, 15(12), 1619. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci15121619>
- Tang, J., Liu, Y., & Chen, H. (2025). Motivational regulation and SRL strategy use among college EFL learners. *Learning and Instruction*, 85, 101763. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.learninstruc.2023.101763>
- Teng, F. (2022). Metacognitive awareness and oral English proficiency. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 13, 824235. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/330474908>
- Teng, M. F. (2022). Contextual sensitivity and oral communication performance among EFL learners. *Applied Linguistics Review*, 13(2), 289–312. <https://doi.org/10.1515/applirev-2020-0085>
- Teng, M. F., Mizumoto, A., & Takeuchi, O. (2024). Growth mindset and self-regulated vocabulary learning. *System*, 122, 103255. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2024.103255>
- Torrevillas, J. (2022). Oral language proficiency: Basis for material design and development. *International Journal of Language and Literary Studies*, 4(1), 122–135. <https://doi.org/10.36892/ijlls.v4i1.749>
- Uchihara, T., & Saito, K. (2021). The relationship between vocabulary size and second language speech fluency and comprehensibility. *Language Learning*, 71(2), 447–485. <https://www.researchgate.net/publication/303290146>
- Uchihara, T., & Saito, K. (2021). Exploring the relationship between vocabulary knowledge and spoken language comprehensibility. *The Modern Language Journal*, 105(1), 335–352. <https://doi.org/10.1111/modl.12690>
- Walach, M. (2020). Environmental regulation as a facet of self-regulated learning in academic performance. *Frontiers in Education*, 5, 37. <https://doi.org/10.3389/educ.2020.00037>
- Xu, X., Zheng, C., & Wang, Z. (2022). Self-regulated learning strategies in oral presentations among EFL undergraduates. *System*, 107, 102824. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.system.2022.102824>
- Zepeda, C. D., Richey, J. E., Ronevich, P., & Nokes-Malach, T. J. (2020). Direct instruction of metacognition benefits academic performance and transfer of learning. *Journal of Educational Psychology*, 112(4), 695–709. <https://psycnet.apa.org/doiLanding?doi=10.1037%2Fedu0000407>
- Zepeda, C. D., Martin, R. S., & Butler, A. C. (2020). Metacognitive strategy instruction improves students' monitoring and use of learning strategies in academic settings. *Journal of Applied Research in Memory and Cognition*, 9(4), 429–443. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jarmac.2020.07.008>
- Zhang, T. (2024). Effects of self-regulation strategies on EFL learners' motivation, self-efficacy, willingness to communicate, and creativity. *BMC Psychology*, 12, Article 75. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40359-024-01567-2>
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2020). Becoming a self-regulated learner: An overview. *Theory Into Practice*, 59(1), 1–11.

-
- Zimmerman, B. J. (2020). Self-regulation of learning: Zimmerman's model revisited. In D. H. Schunk & J. A. Greene (Eds.), *Handbook of self-regulation of learning and performance* (2nd ed., pp. 1–16). Routledge.
- Zimmerman, B. J., & Schunk, D. H. (2021). Self-regulated learning and academic achievement: Theoretical perspectives (3rd ed.). *Contemporary Educational Psychology*, 64, 101924. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cedpsych.2020.101924>